

The Poetics of Wormholes

The door schematizes two strong possibilities [...] at times, it is closed, bolted, padlocked. At others, it is open, that is to say, wide open.

– Gaston Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*

Alice presses her hands up to the looking-glass and in a moment she is through [...] sent swirling along a chaotic vortex of fire and lightning [...] ejected from a nebulous, sphincter-like opening [...] onto the other side of the US-Mexico border [...] where the next leap may be the leap home.

– various, remixed

In *The Poetics of Space*, Gaston Bachelard explores the power of “poetic images” that form the foundation of our phenomenological experience of space.¹ Demonstrating their ubiquity through examples in poetry, Bachelard suggests that these poetic spatialities can give us insight into the articulation of primal metaphors: the nest as well-fitting shelter, the shell as body inhabited by a soul.

If things as common-place as nests and shells resonate with a rich poetic dynamism, then what desires and apprehensions, spatial dreams and fantasies clamour around something as exotic and super-natural as a Wormhole?

The following is an preliminary reconnaissance of wormholes, taking Bachelard's *topoanalysis* – the systematic psychological study of sites – as a point-of-departure. It forms a tentative 'Poetics of Wormholes' exploring the imaginative significance of the wormhole beyond its literal definition, using science fiction rather than poetry as a source of reference material.

¹ Bachelard, Gaston, and M. Jolas. *The Poetics of Space*. Boston: Beacon Press, 1994.

Supplementary dimensions

'Wormhole' describes a diverse set of speculative and fantastic models for physical phenomena; from conservation-of-momentum-consistent portals² to passages through nightmarish meta-space³.

To set the scope, I will define a wormhole as the connection of two points on n -dimensional space via a supplementary dimension. This is concise, but also conveniently inclusive. Our portal gun creates wormholes that fit the cool-headed scientific definition (*figure 1*):

A hypothetical "tunnel" connecting two different points in spacetime in such a way that a trip through the wormhole could take much less time than a journey between the same starting and ending points in normal space.⁴

While a literal worm-hole joins two points on a plane (the ground) via a passage through the supplementary dimension of depth (through earth).

Figure 1 Diagram of a wormhole graphic (*The Encyclopaedia of Science*)

Different imaginings of wormholes express very different concepts of

² For example from *Portal* and *Portal 2*.

³ Examples in *Flight of the Navigator* and *Doctor Who* series 6.

⁴ David Darling, *The Encyclopaedia of Science*.

spatiality, but we shouldn't forget the more mundane source of the metaphor either: worm-holes, tunnels, and the subterranean still hold meaningful resonance, most especially in their shared resistance to rationality and legibility. This resistance is fundamental to the spatial behaviour of a wormhole: from observable space (whether it's a plane, or space-time) it appears unpredictable, hidden, and exceptional.

Spatiality and Directionality

Wormholes operate with an ambiguous inside-outside spatiality. They can be legitimately perceived as both an *entrance into* another locality (or hyperspace), or an *exit from* this locality. Bachelard expresses this ambiguity as one that operates even with normal doorways, speaking of “this side” and “beyond”, and denying the two terms’ reciprocity.

Doors can be both barriers against or portals to the “beyond”, and there is a rich vocabulary of feelings sited at the threshold, formed by their state. When “closed, bolted, padlocked” they may make us feel claustrophobic, imprisoned, or they may offer the promise of an unknown treasure. The protagonists of a story may spend considerable time and effort in the goal of opening the portal, as in *Stargate*. When “wide open” the door may offer escape, as the portal-gun does for the test subject trapped by a malevolent AI in the game *Portal*, or we may feel agoraphobic; threatened by what is *beyond* and what may try to get to *this side*. The drama of a story may centre on trying to close a wormhole that was opened with cavalier hubris, by those seduced with “the temptation to open up the ultimate depths”, such as the portal to hell in *Doom 3* and the *Evil Dead* series, or to the domain of a violent alien presence such as the extra-universal wormhole in *Babylon 5: Thirdspace*.

When a wormhole allows only uni-directional travel, its spatiality becomes that of linear progression; a model for digestion, 'burning bridges', or rebirth that may often include a dangerous trial-by-fire⁵ (*Figure 2*). The leap of faith required to journey through such a wormhole is well articulated by threshold surfaces such as the mercury-like liquid mirror of a Stargate, or the pliant looking-glass that Alice pushes through. In these examples, not only must the traveller overcome the primal fear of drowning to “take the plunge”, but they must literally face themselves (confronting their mirror image) to do so.

⁵ Examples in Flight of the Navigator and Doctor Who series 6.

Figure 2 Opening title for *Doctor Who* series 6

Exceptions

Wormholes are sites of exception. In the literal sense, they are an apparent exception to the physical continuity of n -dimensional space, via their $n+1$ dimensionality. Beyond their functional existence within narratives, as poetic images they express exceptions of other kinds.

Authority

An authority controls space, according to Michel de Certeau, by isolating it from its surrounding landscape, surveying it, and conceptualising it as an abstract territory within which action can be strategically planned.⁶ Boundaries such as the US-Mexico border are drawn up within an abstracted, 2-dimensional, isotropic model of space; a snaking line on the map.

Figure 3 Mexican drug smuggler tunnel entrance.⁷

Wormholes have a prodigious history of operating out of sight of authority:

⁶ Certeau, Michel de. *The Practice of Everyday Life*. . Translated by Steven Rendall: University of California Press., 2002.

⁷ Wilson, Simone, "Top 10 U.S. Customs Seizures Of 2010, Including \$9 Million Train-Load Of Pot In California", *LAWeekly*, January 5, 2011. Retrieved from <https://www.laweekly.com/news/top-10-us-customs-seizures-of-2010-including-9-million-train-load-of-pot-in-california-2391724>

from eighteenth century pirate smuggling tunnels of Cornwall, to those of today (*figure 3*), wormholes clandestinely connect disparate localities across seemingly impervious bureaucratic boundaries. The space wormholes traverse exists outside of the conventional surveyed and mapped world, and thus out of the scope of Authority. On the ground, the barrier that exercises customs duty or enforces prohibition seems solid, but somewhere along a supplementary dimension the map can be quietly folded to form a wormhole.

Reason

Science-fiction has often richly explored the consequences of speculative technologies years before they become part of our everyday lives. The communicator used by Capt. Kirk, and Arthur C. Clark's geostationary satellites have allowed the audience/reader to become familiar with novel concepts and the author to 'feel-out' the psychological and sociological implications of new technology.

In *Portal* the underlying dynamics of wormholes are clear, allowing the player to explore the physical possibilities of the phenomenon. One space is joined seamlessly to the other, and objects moving between the two maintain their momentum relative to the alignment of the portal.⁸(*Figure 4*) The portals themselves are rational, predictable, and legible, and it is a central part of the game narrative that the human protagonist is the surprising, non-linear element in the environment.

⁸ Opened by the portal-gun in the games *Portal* and *Portal 2*.

Figure 4 Illustration of portals in *Portal: No Escape*, Dan Trachtenberg, 2011

In contrast, the appearance of wormholes in stories can also allow a space for mystery and the unknown in a genre where scientific knowledge is expected to give a comprehensive, rational explanation of the universe: things get more dramatic and interesting when the Positivism of *Star Trek TNG's* Enterprise crew is thwarted by an object that is inexplicably invisible to their sensors.

Wormholes are elements of exotic, non-newtonian physics. Whether or not their behaviour is consistent with theoretical models, it's certainly not consistent with our intuitive understanding of space. Even caves and subterranean passages, which sit happily within conventional space, seem mysterious and unfathomable, as Bachelard discovers:

[The cellar] is first and foremost the dark entity of the house, the one that partakes in subterranean forces. When we dream there, we are in harmony with the irrationality of the depths.⁹

When Jules Verne's characters journey to centre of the earth in the eponymous story¹⁰ they enter a volcanic tube in an extinct Icelandic volcano and are surprised to find themselves emerging in southern Italy. When Col. O'Neil and his team pass through the primed Stargate housed in a top-secret military complex deep underground they are similarly surprised to emerge

⁹ Bachelard, Gaston, and M. Jolas. *The Poetics of Space*. Boston: Beacon Press, 1994.

¹⁰ Verne, J. A. *Journey to the Center of the Earth: Signet Classics*, 2003.

on an alien planet on the other side of the known universe.

The super-natural, other-worldly “irrationality of the depths” resonates with the occult through the ritual magic of gates and portals. The Stargate found amongst the artefacts of ancient Egyptian civilisation is the product of a seemingly god-like alien race where technology and magic are blurred, opened using arcane knowledge; in William Gibson's *Count Zero*, the spirit Papa Legba stands at the gateway to cyberspace, and is summoned by drawing an elaborate Voodoo pattern known as a *vévé*; in *Farscape* the wormhole knowledge of an ancient, lost alien species has been implanted into John Crichton's subconscious, only accessible through intuition and dreams; in *Flight of the Navigator* the events between David's departure through hyperspace and his final return happen outside of local time, allowing for the possibility that it was all a dream, just as Alice's trip to Wonderland could have been.

With this connection to the occult, it seems appropriate that wormholes have been used in sci-fi as a plot device and occasional *deus ex machina* to solve difficult situations.

Meaning

Wormholes, while an exception from reason, are meaningful. In fact, their meaning is tied to the inexplicable.

Of course, wormholes of a certain type *can* be explained, but as illustrated above, the mechanisms through which wormholes operate in science fiction are often deliberately inexplicable.

For Bachelard, the door has its own agency: “incarnated in the door, there is a little threshold god”. In our experience of everyday doors, this mythology of psychism forms part of a psychological investment in the thresholds and the symbolic power they hold: they are deeply meaningful. Traditional themes such as gateways that only allow pure souls, have a mystic agency, or are magically invoked are retold with Sci-Fi accoutrements.

In *Deep Space 9* for example, the Bajoran wormhole is a surprising discovery: the only stable wormhole in the universe. It becomes the focus of scientific investigation by the crew of a research space station (“Deep Space 9”). It is later revealed that the wormhole was constructed by non-corporeal beings known as Prophets who exist outside of time and space, are worshipped as gods, and can perform (what appear to be) miracles at opportune moments to save the story's protagonists: literal *Deus Ex Machina*.

Similarly, in *Quantum Leap*, Sam Beckett's involuntary and irreversible leap into the unknown eventually explains itself as divine influence. The journey through space-time to “put right what once went wrong” ends up being not so much the reasonable, but the profoundly meaningful purpose of the wormhole.

While the advanced technological development typically featured in science fiction answers practical questions of life, the unexplainable leaves room for

an overarching meaningfulness to events, whether through the influence of ancient benevolent aliens or the divine.

Final Thoughts

...where the next leap may be the leap home.

Wormholes offer a way of interrogating our phenomenological experience of space: our apprehensions and desires writ large through hyperbolic exaggerations of the *beyond* and the unknown. However while they occasionally set up such unfamiliar scenarios as time paradoxes, as poetic images they don't extend far beyond the richness of the domestic domain examined by Bachelard. They simply provide a contemporary replacement for the caves, tunnels, mythical portal, et al.

Maybe this isn't surprising. Bachelard considered the house “an instrument with which to confront the cosmos”¹¹, and the easy application of the poetic images of doors and cellars to stories of wormholes might be a continuation of our understanding of all spatiality through our earliest phenomenological experience. In exotic spatial phenomenon and stories at the galactic scale we are still making reference to 'Home'.

¹¹ Bachelard, Gaston, and M. Jolas. *The Poetics of Space*. Boston: Beacon Press, 1994, 46.